

Viper Snake Envenomation Induced Unilateral Trigeminal Neuropathy in a Golden Retriever Dog

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Abstract

A 2-year-old Golden Retriever dog was presented with the history of a snake bite by a viper. On clinical examination, the animal had fang marks on the forehead region, bleeding from injection sites, swelling and drooping of the right eyelid, along with weakness of the ipsilateral side of the face. The case was diagnosed as Viper Snake Venom-Induced Unilateral Trigeminal Neuropathy due to the anatomical location of bite injury. The animal was treated with two doses of polyvalent anti-snake venom, fluids, tetanus toxoid, antibiotics, diuretics, phenylephrine eye drops, hepatoprotectants and neurotonics. The animal responded well to the treatment and recovered completely.

Keywords: Snake envenomation, Neuropathy, dog, anti-snake venom

Introduction

Snake bite in dogs generally occurs during hunting or while playing in the garden. Identification of the snake helps in the rapid and appropriate treatment of the snake bite. Vipers are members of the family *Viperidae*, which are characterized by a pair of long, hollow, venom-injecting fangs. Severity of the snakebite depends on the location, depth and number of

bites, the amount of venom injected, the species, size and age of the snake, the age and the size of the victim, the victim's sensitivity to venom, and the type of first aid treatment and subsequent medical care (Gold *et al.*, 2002). Viper's teeth penetration marks were observed in 44% of the dogs when envenomated in the head and submandibular area, and in 75% of the dogs envenomated in the limbs (Segev *et al.*, 2004).

Neurotoxins are the major component of elapids' venom, of which beta neurotoxins inhibit the release of acetylcholine from presynaptic terminals irreversibly. The examples of beta neurotoxins include taipoxin, paradoxin, trimucrotoxin, viperotoxin, pseudocerastes, textilotoxin and crotoxin. Whereas, alpha-neurotoxins causes reversible blockage of acetylcholine receptors, example, iridotoxin (Del Brutto and Del Brutto, 2012). Seneviratne and Dissanayake (2002) and Patil *et al.* (2011) reported the neurological manifestations of snake bite human cases in Sri Lanka and India, respectively. Mathias *et al.* (2022) reported acute peripheral neuropathy following animal envenomation in human snakebite cases. Martins *et al.* (2016) and Pandit *et al.* (2024) have described the neurological and neuro-ophthalmological manifestations of snake bite human cases. Baig *et al.* (2009) reported an unusual case of acute neuropathy in a 48-year-old man following Russell's viper envenomation. However, the neurological manifestations in dogs caused by viper bite has not been reported in veterinary literature. This report presents the unilateral ptosis and weakness of facial muscles in a viper envenomated dog.

Case History and Observations

A 2-year-old, Golden Retriever, male, intact dog weighing 30 kgs was brought to the critical care unit of the Madras Veterinary College Teaching Hospital with the history of a snake bite by a viper. On examination of the animal's fang marks with inflammatory changes on the forehead region (**Fig 1**), swelling and ptosis of the right eyelid, ipsilateral weakness of the face (**Fig. 2**) and signs of DIC were noticed. The animal had tachypnea, and all other vital parameters were within the normal range. The haematological and serum biochemical parameters showed leukocytosis (33,800 cells/cmm), neutrophilia, echinocytosis (**Fig.3**) and elevated levels of ALT (161 IU/dL) and ALP (607 IU/dL). The bronchial pattern was visualized on the thoracic radiograph. On the coagulation profile, the animal had a prothrombin time of 11.6 seconds and an

activated partial thromboplastin time of 59.5 seconds. Based on history, clinical observations and laboratory findings, the case was diagnosed as viper snake venom-induced unilateral trigeminal neuropathy due to the anatomical location of the bite injury.

Treatment and Discussion

Intensive therapy should be instituted as soon as possible because the irreversible effects of venom begin immediately after envenomation. Polyvalent anti-snake venom was administered to neutralize the viper venom. As a prophylaxis, tetanus toxoid (0.5ml I/M) and broad-spectrum antibiotic (Amoxicillin @ 15mg/kg, q12h) were administered to the patient, as the fangs of the snake are supposed to be contaminated with various types of bacteria. Ptosis was managed successfully with phenylephrine eye drops (three drops thrice a day for 3 weeks). Supportive therapy included fluids, analgesics, diuretics, hepatoprotectants and neurotonics. Early diagnosis and treatment led to the successful recovery of the dog with complete resorption of clinical signs.

Snake venoms are a complex mixture of proteins and peptides, consisting of both enzymatic and non-enzymatic compounds. Klaassenn (2008) described that the hyaluronidase in the venom cleaves the internal glycoside bonds in certain acid mucopolysaccharides, resulting in decreased viscosity of connective tissues, allowing other fractions of venom to penetrate the tissues. Aroch and Harrus (1999) and Day *et al.* (2025) reported the most common clinical signs and complications. The common local signs in viper bite include swelling, oedema and hematoma, which are attributed mostly to venom hemorrhagic activity, and systemic signs include anaphylactic, hemorrhagic or neurogenic shock, tachypnea, tachycardia, local lymphadenomegaly and cardiac arrhythmias. The most common complications reported include bacterial infections (clostridial or other), local necrosis, upper respiratory airway obstruction due to laryngeal oedema, disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC), acute renal failure, severe thrombocytopenia and death. Hackett *et al.* (2002) reported

echinocytosis in more than 90% of dogs envenomated by rattlesnakes. Del Brutto and Del Brutto (2012) described the common neurological complications of venomous snake bites in human beings. Murmu *et al.* (2025) evaluation of myotoxicity and neuropathy in hemotoxic snake bite envenomation in human. Kularatne (2003) reported ptosis in 78% of the Russell's viper envenomated human patients. Viper bites caused an isolated ptosis and lower motor neuron type facial nerve palsy (Chakrabarti, 2012; Blasco Marino *et al.*, 2022). The most effective antidote against snake venom is the polyvalent anti-snake venom, which neutralizes the venom of different species of snakes.

Summary

A rare case of viper snake envenomation-induced unilateral trigeminal neuropathy and its successful therapeutic management is reported in a Golden Retriever dog.

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Fig. 1. Fang marks on forehead region

Fig. 2. Ptosis and weakness of the right side of the face

Fig. 3. Echinocytes of RBCs on Blood Smear examination

